

Hidden Markov Models for Bounded, Inflated Time Series: Forecasting Icing on Wind Turbine Blades

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Abstract

Time series analysis of icing-induced power loss in wind turbines pose several challenges: the response is bounded, serially dependent, intermittently missing, highly dispersed, and often inflated at a single value. We address these challenges with discrete-time hidden Markov models for a discrete-continuous process assumed to follow a mixture of state-dependent zero-inflated beta distributions. The framework allows covariates to influence either the transition probabilities or the distribution parameters. In a case study, we evaluate 12-hour ahead forecasts of icing-related power loss. Compared to autoregressive and regression baselines, the proposed model achieves the highest predictive accuracy.

Keywords: Probabilistic forecast; Zero-inflated beta distribution; Latent mixture models; Ice accretion; Wind power; Power loss

1 Introduction

In cold climates, ice occasionally accretes on the blades of wind turbines, slowing their rotation. This leads to substantial decreases in power production (Gao and Hu, 2021). When this happens, traditional forecasting methods overestimate power production. Consequently, the owner of the wind farm must balance out their production deficit by purchasing additional power on the short-term spot market, which creates an additional layer of icing-induced economic losses.

It is not straightforward to measure the physical load of the accreted ice on the blades of wind turbines (Davis et al., 2013). Therefore, proxies for physical ice levels are often derived from the difference between the expected power output (based on measured weather conditions) and the observed power output from the plant (Davis et al., 2014). Figure 1 shows an example of icing-induced power loss for a winter as time series and histograms of the empirical distribution. Icing is largely undetected, which implies that the wind power plant operates normally most of the time. Under these conditions, icing-induced power loss is zero, resulting in the heavy zero-inflation. However, when icing events do occur, they can cause a significant reduction in power

Figure 1: Icing-induced power loss (y) shown as a time series as well as in a histogram of all measurements (i.e. $y \in [0, 1]$) and a histogram of icing where normal operation is excluded (i.e. $y \in (0, 1]$).

30 production, with losses up to 100%. Consequently, the icing signal is a *bounded* response variable. Missing
 31 values are occasionally observed during the winter season, both during normal operation and icing events. The
 32 duration of icing events varies. Some are brief, with a rapid increase in relative power loss that quickly returns
 33 to zero. Others persist longer, exhibiting multiple peaks before normal operation resumes. This variability
 34 reflects a high dispersion of the response variable.

35 Times series like the icing signal pose awkward hurdles in dynamical statistical modeling due to the bounded
 36 domain of the response variable, missing observations, large dispersion, and zero-inflation. Typically, transfor-
 37 mations are used to make the data appear Gaussian to align with assumptions of standard time series models
 38 (e.g. ARIMA types). Missing observations are imputed via interpolation techniques. Although such preprocess-
 39 ing sometimes is capable of remedying mismatches between standard models and data, it does usually not
 40 address the underlying structure of the data which requires more complex models. For example, using probabil-
 41 ity distributions that closely resemble the empirical one, we obtain a more accurate description of uncertainty,
 42 which is valuable in situations where we want to predict a future event (Gneiting and Katzfuss, 2014).

43 1.1 Forecasting icing on wind turbine blades

44 Bergström et al. (2013) show that the mass of accreted ice and the power loss are only weakly correlated.
 45 However, they suggest that ice growth is better correlated with production loss. Davis et al. (2016) applied
 46 hierarchical generalized additive models to predict icing-induced production loss using the output from a phys-
 47 ical ice model as input together with pressure, temperature, and wind speed. In that way, they address the
 48 unknown relationship between physical properties of accreted ice (mass, duration, density) and production loss
 49 by combining a statistical and physical approach such that the output from a physical model is incorporated

50 as input in a statistical one. Scher and Molinder (2019) compared four different machine learning algorithms
51 for the prediction of power loss. They consider multiple linear regression, random forest regression, support
52 vector regression, and neural networks with a hidden layer, all using input from a physical ice model and NWP.
53 However, none of these methods explicitly accounts for the bounded and inflated distribution of the power loss
54 signal. Random forest regression proved to have the best forecast performance of the approaches studied, but
55 its use had some major drawbacks. For example, its forecast performance is not better than a persistence
56 model (basic reference predictor) for 12-hour ahead predictions (Scher and Molinder, 2019). Additionally, its
57 non-parametric model formulation makes interpretation difficult (Scher and Molinder, 2019). Lastly, forest
58 regression is not suitable for handling missing information, which is why imputation techniques are required
59 for preprocessing. Hidden Markov models have not previously been used to predict ice-induced power loss on
60 wind turbines, although they are inherently well suited to account for both temporal dependence and high
61 dispersion, as well as suitable for the modeler to specify a parametric probability distribution in accordance
62 with the empirical one.

63 Additionally, many of the authors propose mathematical models where some inputs are provided by a first-
64 principle model of ice accretion (Scher and Molinder, 2019; Molinder et al., 2018; Strauss et al., 2022; Davis
65 et al., 2016), e.g. relying on computational fluid dynamics for ice accretion modeling (Morency et al., 2001),
66 energy balance equations expressing ice accretion as a free-boundary-value problem (or Stefan problem) in a
67 setting of partial differential equations (Myers, 2001), or by empirical relationships for estimating the fraction
68 of incoming particles impacting a cylinder object given wind speed, object, and droplet size (Makkonen, 2000).
69 Simulations of such physical models are computationally expensive compared to statistical models, because
70 they require input that needs to be generated by a mesoscale (or regional) numerical weather model such as the
71 Weather Research & Forecasting Model (Skamarock et al., 2019) or HARMONIE-AROME (Bengtsson et al.,
72 2017). However, industrial forecasters are often in a position where such computationally expensive simulations
73 are not feasible for real-time forecast operation. Instead, they rely on widely available larger grid predictions
74 from global models, such as the ECMWF HRES (ECMWF, 2023a).

75 **1.2 Beta distribution and zero-inflation**

76 The beta distribution is the standard distribution for continuous and bounded random variables (Pitman,
77 1993). This makes it a natural candidate for bounded processes such as icing-induced power loss. Other
78 alternatives exist, such as the truncated Gaussian or the Kumaraswamy distribution, but the beta distribution
79 will be considered in the present study due to its tail flexibility and widespread use in modeling bounded data
80 (Thyregod and Madsen, 2006).

81 The beta model was proposed for regression of bounded response variables by Ferrari and Cribari-Neto
82 (2004) arguing for its great versatility and applicability for asymmetric and bounded data. Ma and Leijon
83 (2009) incorporate the beta distribution in mixture models, allowing for (possibly multimodal) modeling of
84 data with large dispersion. Temporal dependence is not considered by such model types. However, Rocha and

85 Cribari-Neto (2009) introduced beta autoregressive moving average models that account for temporal dynamics,
86 yet without latent variables or modeling of single-value inflation. Zero-one-inflated beta regression models were
87 proposed by Ospina and Ferrari (2012) to model proportions suffering from an excess of 0-values and/or 1-values;
88 however, without taking into account potential temporal dynamics.

89 **1.3 Hidden Markov models with covariates**

90 Discrete-time hidden Markov models with finite state space have been widely applied within time series fore-
91 casting due to their ability to capture temporal dynamics under flexible probabilistic settings with an inherent
92 ability to handle missing observations in data (Zucchini and MacDonald, 2009). As a preponderance of zeros
93 in classical time series analysis introduces modeling issues, zero inflation has previously been introduced to
94 the HMM setting, most dominantly with the Poisson distribution (Desantis and Bandyopadhyay, 2011). It is
95 less common with latent mixtures of beta distributions, but we found one study by Alerini et al. (2017) that
96 incorporates a zero-inflated beta distribution in an HMM. However, the study does not consider covariates and
97 the model is not applied for forecasting purposes.

98 The two most predominant ways of incorporating covariates in an HMM is by regressing either the transi-
99 tion probabilities (Meligkotsidou and Dellaportas, 2011) or the density parameters of a parametric distribution
100 (Punzo et al., 2018) on exogenous information. Usually, covariate-dependency is introduced via the transition
101 rates as this methodology preserves best interpretability (Zucchini and MacDonald, 2009). The two approaches
102 are rarely compared, and we found no study that demonstrates which of the two offers better predictive perfor-
103 mance.

104 **1.4 Forecast evaluation**

105 Many forecasting studies do not include simple reference predictors (Hewamalage et al., 2023; Hyndman, 2010),
106 which makes it harder to demonstrate the practical usefulness of developed methodologies. A decent baseline
107 should represent basic predictability. The forecast performance of simple models is often better than that of
108 more complex models (Kilian and Taylor, 2003; Merkle et al., 2020; Ascher, 1981; Scher and Molinder, 2019).
109 Although Meligkotsidou and Dellaportas (2011) apply appropriate scoring rules for evaluating the predictive
110 densities of the proposed models, the reference forecast is an HMM itself why the general applicability of
111 the latent and dynamic model setting is left to be demonstrated. Benchmarking a complex model against
112 an even more complex one without providing evidence of what is actually gained (compared to, e.g., random
113 walks, threshold, or persistence models) is an issue in forecasting, as it leaves the practical value yet to be
114 demonstrated (Hewamalage et al., 2023). A review paper by Green and Armstrong (2015) found that introducing
115 model complexity actually increases forecast errors by 27% on average. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the
116 increase in accuracy when increasing model complexity. We did not find any study that performed a probabilistic
117 forecast evaluation of predictive mixed densities of discrete-continuous type. Indeed, most literature related to
118 icing on wind turbine blades evaluates forecast performance with point-based metrics such as root-mean square

119 error (RMSE) or mean absolute error (MAE) (Scher and Molinder, 2019; Davis et al., 2016; Molinder et al.,
 120 2018); however, with few exceptions such as (Strauss et al., 2022) who apply the continuous ranked probability
 121 score (CRPS) for ensemble forecasts.

122 1.5 Outline and contributions

123 This study proposes a discrete-time hidden Markov model (HMM) with state-dependent zero-inflated beta
 124 (ZIB) distributions for forecasting power loss in wind turbines caused by icing events. Compared to existing
 125 approaches, our contribution is twofold:

- 126 • Methodological novelty. We extend the use of ZIB HMMs to a forecasting setting, addressing the chal-
 127 lenges of icing signals. Bounded support, zero inflation, and high dispersion are accounted for using the
 128 mixture of zero-inflated beta distributions; serial dependence is modeled through the latent state dynam-
 129 ics. Missing values in the response variable are handled naturally within the HMM framework, which
 130 allows likelihood computation without the need for imputation. We explore two covariate-dependent ex-
 131 tensions, regression on transition probabilities and regression on state-dependent densities, and investigate
 132 their implications for forecast accuracy and interpretability.
- 133 • Practical relevance. We demonstrate the applicability of the proposed framework in an industrial case
 134 study using operational data from multiple wind farms. By benchmarking against autoregressive and
 135 regression-type baselines, we show that ZIB HMMs yield more accurate probabilistic forecasts, which
 136 can improve short-term power production planning and risk management during icing events.

137 The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we present the ZIB HMM framework, including regression
 138 settings, estimation methodology, and forecasting setup. Section 3 details the evaluation metrics for probabilistic
 139 forecasts of discrete-continuous type and describes the reference predictors. Section 4 applies the models to the
 140 case study of icing-induced power loss and reports comparative results, with discussions of implications for
 141 forecasting practice.

142 2 Proposed model

143 We define a stochastic and continuous process $\{Y_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$ on $[0,1)$ assumed to follow a zero-inflated beta
 144 distribution. Thus, it has the probability density function

$$f_{Y_t}(y; \mu, \phi, p) = \begin{cases} p, & y = 0, \\ (1-p)B(y; \mu, \phi), & 0 < y < 1, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

145 with the beta density given by

$$B(y; \mu, \phi) = \frac{\Gamma(\phi)}{\Gamma(\mu\phi)\Gamma((1-\mu)\phi)} y^{\mu\phi-1} (1-y)^{(1-\mu)\phi-1},$$

146 where $0 < \mu < 1$, $\phi > 0$, $0 < p < 1$, and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function. Equivalently, we say that $Y_t \sim \mathcal{ZIB}(\mu, \phi, p)$.
 147 Eq. (1) is a mixture between a beta density and a probability mass. Therefore, it is said to be a discrete-
 148 continuous distribution.

149 2.1 Dynamic mixture setting

150 To account for serial dependence and possible overdispersion in times series data, we introduce the dynamic
 151 mixture setting of an HMM. Assume that the discrete stochastic process $\{C_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$ switches between m
 152 hidden states. The latent process satisfies the Markov property, that is

$$Pr(C_t | \mathbf{C}^{(t-1)}) = Pr(C_t | C_{t-1}), \quad t = 2, 3, \dots, \quad (2)$$

153 where $\mathbf{C}^{(t-1)}$ denotes the history from time 1 to $t - 1$ of the process $\{C_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$. The probability of
 154 transitioning from state i to state j is $\pi_{ij} = Pr(C_t = j | C_{t-1} = i)$. The transition probabilities constitute
 155 all (i, j) -elements in the transition probability matrix $\mathbf{\Pi}$ of size $m \times m$. Given the distribution at time t ,
 156 $\mathbf{u}(t) = (Pr(C_t = 1), \dots, Pr(C_t = m))$, of the latent process, the distribution at time $t + 1$ can be found by
 157 post-multiplying with $\mathbf{\Pi}$ such that

$$\mathbf{u}(t + 1) = \mathbf{u}(t)\mathbf{\Pi}.$$

158 The transition probabilities must satisfy that

$$\sum_{j=1}^m \pi_{ij} = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \pi_{ij} \geq 0. \quad (3)$$

One way to enforce these constraints is to work with an unconstrained set of parameters $\tau_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}$ and transform
 them through a row-wise softmax transformation, that is a mapping, $h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, 1)$. Specifically,

$$\pi_{ij} = h(\tau_{ij}) = \frac{\exp(\tau_{ij})}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp(\tau_{ik})}, \quad i = 1, \dots, m,$$

159 with the convention that $\tau_{ii} = 0$, leading to the transition probability matrix

$$\mathbf{\Pi} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{1k}} & \frac{\exp \tau_{12}}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{1k}} & \cdots & \frac{\exp \tau_{1m}}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{1k}} \\ \frac{\exp \tau_{21}}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{2k}} & \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{2k}} & \cdots & \frac{\exp \tau_{2m}}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{2k}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\exp \tau_{m1}}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{mk}} & \frac{\exp \tau_{m2}}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{mk}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \tau_{mk}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

160 which ensures that the constraints in Eq. (3) are fulfilled for all $\tau_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}$: all entries are nonnegative because
 161 the exponential is strictly positive, and the row sum is 1 by construction. Since $\tau_{ii} = 0$, the number of free
 162 parameters reduces to $m(m - 1)$, because the i 'th element in the i 'th row can be obtained by subtracting all

163 off-diagonal elements (in the i 'th row) from 1.

164 We let the continuous stochastic process $\{Y_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$ depend on the Markov chain $\{C_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$ such that

$$f_{Y_t | \mathbf{Y}^{(t-1)}, \mathbf{C}^{(t)}}(y) = f_{Y_t | C_t}(y), \quad t = 1, 2, \dots \quad (5)$$

165 where $\mathbf{Y}^{(t-1)}$ denotes the history from time 1 to $t-1$ of the process $\{Y_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$. We say that $Y_t | C_t = i \sim$
 166 $\mathcal{ZIB}(\mu^{(i)}, \phi^{(i)}, p^{(i)})$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$. Thus, Y_t is distributed according to a mixture of state-dependent zero-
 167 inflated beta distributions conditioned on the time-dependent hidden process C_t . In total, this zero-inflated
 168 beta distributed HMM without covariates leaves $3m + m(m-1)$ parameters to be estimated.

169 2.2 Regression setting

170 It is common to incorporate covariates in HHMs through 1) the density parameters of the state-dependent
 171 distributions or 2) the transition probabilities. These two probabilistic dependency settings are visualized in
 172 Fig. 2 with dashed lines provided a multivariate covariate set $\mathbf{V}_t \in \mathbb{R}^q$ where q is the number of exogenous
 variables.

Figure 2: Hidden Markov model with covariates in a directed and acyclic graph. Covariates are included either in the state-dependent densities or in the transition probabilities of the hidden process, indicated by dashed lines.

173

174 2.2.1 Regression via state-dependent distributions

175 Say that three (not necessarily mutually exclusive) sets of exogenous variables are at hand, that is, $\mathbf{X}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{q_1}$,
 176 $\mathbf{Z}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{q_2}$, and $\mathbf{W}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{q_3}$. Assuming that the density in Eq. (1) is a function of these random variables for each
 177 latent state, the density parameters become time-varying when regressed on that information via link functions.
 178 For $i = 1, \dots, m$, say that $\mu_t^{(i)}$ depends on \mathbf{X}_t , $\phi_t^{(i)}$ depends on \mathbf{Z}_t , and $p_t^{(i)}$ depends on \mathbf{W}_t for $t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\mu_t^{(i)} = g_1 \left(\beta_0^{(i)} + \mathbf{X}_t^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^{(i)} \right), \quad \phi_t^{(i)} = g_2 \left(\gamma_0^{(i)} + \mathbf{Z}_t^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}^{(i)} \right), \quad \text{and} \quad p_t^{(i)} = g_3 \left(\rho_0^{(i)} + \mathbf{W}_t^\top \boldsymbol{\rho}^{(i)} \right), \quad (6)$$

179 where $\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(i)} = (\beta_1^{(i)}, \dots, \beta_{q_1}^{(i)})^\top$, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}^{(i)} = (\gamma_1^{(i)}, \dots, \gamma_{q_2}^{(i)})^\top$, and $\boldsymbol{\rho}^{(i)} = (\rho_1^{(i)}, \dots, \rho_{q_3}^{(i)})^\top$ (Ferrari and Cribari-Neto,
 180 2004). Since both $\mu_t^{(i)}$ and $p_t^{(i)}$ are defined on the open unit interval, $g_1(\cdot)$ and $g_3(\cdot)$ are chosen as the sigmoid
 181 function, well-suited for mapping real numbers to probabilities. Since $\phi_t^{(i)} > 0$, $g_2(\cdot)$ is chosen as the softplus

182 function, $g_2(x) = \log(\exp(x) + 1)$, ensuring that $\gamma_0^{(i)} + \mathbf{Z}_t^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}^{(i)}$ is mapped into \mathbb{R}_+ . More details on link functions
183 for regression on parameters in parametric distributions of exponential family are provided by Thyregod and
184 Madsen (2006) in the setting of generalized linear models. Given the dependency setting of Eq. (6), we say that
185 $Y_t | C_t = i \sim \mathcal{ZIB}(\mu_t^{(i)}, \phi_t^{(i)}, p_t^{(i)})$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$, which implies that

$$f_{Y_t | \mathbf{Y}^{(t-1)}, \mathcal{C}^{(t)}, \mathbf{V}^{(t)}}(y) = f_{Y_t | C_t, \mathbf{V}_t}(y), \quad t = 1, 2, \dots,$$

186 where the superscript notation of $\cdot^{(t)}$ is shorthand for the history of the variable up to and including time t .
187 Note that we have adopted the shorthand notation, \mathbf{V}_t , for the total set of unique covariates. Regression on the
188 state-dependent distributions parameters setting does not invoke inhomogeneity of the Markov chain as long as
189 $\boldsymbol{\Pi}$ is kept constant. The total number of model parameters is $(3 + q_1 + q_2 + q_3)m + m(m - 1)$.¹

190 2.2.2 Regression via transition probabilities

191 Instead of regressing the state-dependent density parameters on \mathbf{V}_t , the transition probabilities can be assumed
192 covariate-dependent via the constraint-free τ_{ij} introduced for the parameterization of the transition probability
193 matrix in Eq. (4), i.e.,

$$\tau_{ij} = \eta_0^{(ij)} + \mathbf{V}_t^\top \boldsymbol{\eta}^{(ij)}, \quad i \neq j$$

194 with $\boldsymbol{\eta}^{(ij)} = \left(\eta_1^{(ij)}, \dots, \eta_q^{(ij)} \right)^\top$ denoting the state-to-state-dependent coefficient vector with q elements cor-
195 responding to the size of the row space of \mathbf{V}_t . This regression setting leads to a nonhomogenous Markov
196 chain as the conditional probabilities become time-varying through the covariates. The total number of model
197 parameters is $3m + (q + 1)m(m - 1)$.

198 2.3 The likelihood

199 Given a realization y_1, y_2, \dots, y_T of the process $\{Y_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$, the likelihood is the joint probability density of
200 the observed data evaluated at (y_1, \dots, y_T) , viewed as a function of the model parameters. The likelihood of
201 a hidden Markov model can be calculated as a matrix product of the transition probability matrix and the
202 realizations of Y_t evaluated in the state-dependent densities before summing across all possible states, i.e.

$$L_T = \boldsymbol{\delta} \mathbf{F}_{Y_1}(y_1) \boldsymbol{\Pi}_2 \mathbf{F}_{Y_2}(y_2) \boldsymbol{\Pi}_3 \mathbf{F}_{Y_3}(y_3) \dots \boldsymbol{\Pi}_T \mathbf{F}_{Y_T}(y_T) \mathbf{1}^\top, \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the initial distribution of the chain of size $1 \times m$, $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_t$ is the transition probability matrix, $\mathbf{1}^\top$ is a
transposed vector with all elements equal to 1 of size $m \times 1$, and

$$\mathbf{F}_{Y_t}(y) = \text{diag} \left(f_{Y_t} \left(y; \mu_t^{(i)}, \phi_t^{(i)}, p_t^{(i)} \right), \quad i = 1, \dots, m \right),$$

¹The parameter space can be reduced (see Liisberg et al. (2016)); however, this will not be addressed in the present study.

203 where the density f_{Y_t} is given in Eq. (1) with its parameters linked to the covariates and their corresponding
 204 parameters through Eq. (6). To accommodate an inhomogeneous process given time-varying transition prob-
 205 abilities, some initial condition, $\boldsymbol{\delta}$, must be specified, as it is usually not possible to estimate it consistently
 206 (Turner, 2008).

207 Note that $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_t$ in Eq. (7) has an explicit time dependence to accommodate the regression setting described
 208 in Section 2.2.2. In that case, we assume constant state-dependent density parameters; hence, the explicit
 209 time dependence on $\mu_t^{(i)}$, $\phi_t^{(i)}$, and $p_t^{(i)}$ can be dropped. It is possible to regress both the transition rates
 210 and the density parameters simultaneously, e.g., see Wolf et al. (2019). However, we refrain from such model
 211 extensions in this study. Subsequently, for covariate dependence on the state-dependent densities, we drop the
 212 time-dependence on $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_t$.

213 Unlike discrete-time autoregressive models, HMMs are inherently well-suited for missing observations in
 214 data. In case of a missing observation y_t , the matrix $\mathbf{F}_{Y_t}(y_t)$ is set to the identity matrix which assumes that
 215 the observation is missing by random (Zucchini and MacDonald, 2009).

216 2.3.1 Computing the log-likelihood

217 When computing the likelihood in Eq. (7), the density of all T realizations of the random process $\{Y_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$
 218 in all possible m states must be calculated and then summed across all states. This can be done by a scaled
 219 version of Baum’s forward algorithm, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\psi}_1 &= \frac{\boldsymbol{\delta}\mathbf{F}_{Y_1}(y_1)}{w_1}, \\ w_t\boldsymbol{\psi}_t &= w_{t-1}\boldsymbol{\psi}_{t-1}\boldsymbol{\Pi}_t\mathbf{F}_{Y_t}(y_t), \quad t = 2, \dots, T \\ L_T &= w_T(\boldsymbol{\psi}_T\mathbf{1}^\top) = w_T, \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

220 with $w_t = \boldsymbol{\delta}\mathbf{F}_{Y_1}(y_1) \left(\prod_{s=2}^t \boldsymbol{\Pi}_s\mathbf{F}_{Y_s}(y_s) \right) \mathbf{1}^\top$ and $w_1 = \boldsymbol{\delta}\mathbf{F}_{Y_1}(y_1)\mathbf{1}^\top$, where $\prod_{s=2}^t \mathbf{A}_s := \mathbf{A}_2\mathbf{A}_3 \dots \mathbf{A}_t$ denotes an
 221 ordered product. This leads to the initial distribution $\boldsymbol{\psi}_1 = \boldsymbol{\delta}\mathbf{F}_{Y_1}(y_1)/w_1$. The scaled density at time T is
 222 obtained by recursively updating the scaled forward densities by its previous value multiplied with the transition
 223 probabilities and the state-dependent densities, in each iteration scaling the computation by its vector sum.
 224 Consequently, the log-likelihood ℓ_T can be expressed as

$$\ell_T = \log(w_1) + \sum_{s=2}^T \log(\boldsymbol{\psi}_{s-1}\boldsymbol{\Pi}_s\mathbf{F}_{Y_s}(y_s)\mathbf{1}^\top).$$

225 Lystig and Hughes (2002) show how to compute analytical derivatives via the scaled forward algorithm; however,
 226 in the present study the computation of gradients relies on automatic differentiation (AD) (for further details
 227 see Section 4.3).

2.4 Maximum likelihood estimation

Given T realizations of the stochastic processes Y_t for $t = 1, \dots, T$ and covariates \mathbf{V}_t , we determine the model coefficients by maximum likelihood estimation. The decision variables for this maximization are the parameters related to the transition probability matrix and the state-dependent density parameters. For brevity of notation, we denote the set of parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The maximum likelihood estimation satisfies

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \ell_T. \quad (9)$$

All coefficients associated with the density parameters in the maximization in Eq. (9) are free from constraints because the inverse link functions in Eq. (6) ensure automatic fulfillment of the requirements, i.e., $0 < \mu^{(i)} < 1$, $\phi^{(i)} > 0$, and $0 < p^{(i)} < 1$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$. Similarly, this is the case for the parameters related to the conditional probabilities due to the parameterization of the transition probability matrix via the constraint-free τ_{ij} , ensuring that $\sum_{j=1}^m \pi_{ij} = 1$ and $\pi_{ij} \geq 0$.

2.5 Forecast distribution

To apply the estimated model for h -step prediction, the forecast distribution can be computed at time $T + h$. In this setting, we assume observations of Y_t for $t = 1, \dots, T$ with known covariates \mathbf{V}_t for $t = 1, \dots, T + h$. The forecast distribution of an HMM is given by

$$\begin{aligned} f_{Y_{T+h}|\mathbf{Y}^{(T)},\mathbf{V}^{(T+h)}}(y) &= \boldsymbol{\psi}_T \boldsymbol{\Pi}_{T+1} \boldsymbol{\Pi}_{T+2} \dots \boldsymbol{\Pi}_{T+h} \mathbf{F}_{Y_{T+h}}(y) \mathbf{1}^\top \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^m \xi_{T+h}^{(i)} f_{Y_{T+h}} \left(y; \mu_{T+h}^{(i)}, \phi_{T+h}^{(i)}, p_{T+h}^{(i)} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where the weights $\boldsymbol{\xi}_{T+h} = \boldsymbol{\psi}_T \boldsymbol{\Pi}_{T+1} \boldsymbol{\Pi}_{T+2} \dots \boldsymbol{\Pi}_{T+h}$ are the scaled forward densities (in iteration $t = T$) from the log-likelihood computation post-multiplied with the (possibly time-varying) transition probability matrix h times ahead (Zucchini and MacDonald, 2009). $f_{Y_{T+h}}$ is a mixture of a weighted sum of continuous densities on $y \in (0, 1)$ and probability masses in $y = 0$ (it is mixed by m beta densities and m probability masses) provided the (possibly time-varying) probability density parameters as function of the covariate information, \mathbf{V}_{T+h} .

For $f_{Y_{T+h}}$, we define the associated cumulative distribution function (CDF) as $F_{Y_{T+h}}$. The CDF has particular interest for evaluation purposes. As the beta distribution has no closed-form expression for its CDF, it can either be approximated by discretizing the domain $[0, 1)$ into n equidistant points $y_1 < \dots < y_n$ with $y_1 = 0$ and $y_n = \frac{n-1}{n}$, and evaluating $f_{Y_{T+h}}$ in all those points as a cumulative sum divided by the sample size. However, in this study, the empirical CDF is approximated by drawing n samples from the density $f_{Y_{T+h}|\mathbf{Y}^{(T)},\mathbf{V}^{(T+h)}}$, i.e., (y'_1, \dots, y'_n) . Then

$$\hat{F}_{Y_{T+h}}(y_j) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{1}_{y_i \leq y_j},$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{a \leq b}$ is an indicator function which is 1 when $a \leq b$. As n increases, the empirical CDF approaches the

254 true one, i.e. for $n \rightarrow \infty$, it holds true that $\widehat{F}_{Y_{T+h}} \rightarrow F_{Y_{T+h}}$ asymptotically (Coles, 2001).

255 **3 Forecast evaluation**

256 When evaluating forecast performance, two significant questions arise: 1) What is the reference predictor? and
 257 2) what metric should be used to assess predictive accuracy? (Armstrong, 2001). We begin by discussing the
 258 choice of baseline predictors; evaluation metrics are introduced in Section 3.2.

259 **3.1 Reference predictors**

260 Mittermaier (2008) argues that the persistence model should be use as benchmark to quantify the added
 261 value from a forecast. Indeed, this is the reference predictor considered by Scher and Molinder (2019) when
 262 comparing the predictive performance of the random forest regression for icing-induced power loss on wind
 263 turbines. An even more challenging benchmark to outperform in terms of forecast performance is the first-order
 264 autoregressive process (the AR(1) model), which will be used as a baseline in the forecast evaluation in this
 265 study. The univariate AR(1) model of a stochastic process $\{y_t\}$ is given by

$$y_{t+1} = \rho y_t + \sigma \varepsilon_{t+1}, \quad t \geq 0,$$

266 where $|\rho| < 1$, $\sigma > 0$, and $\varepsilon_{t+1} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. Parameters can be determined by maximum likelihood estimation.
 267 A merit of AR(1) as reference predictor compared to the persistence model is that it assumes a probability
 268 distribution, deeming it applicable for probabilistic evaluation purposes. The forecast distribution of the AR(1)
 269 process is then used to benchmark the results from the *ZIB* HMMs. The h-step predictive distribution of an
 270 AR(1) process is given by

$$f(y_{t+h}|y_t) \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\rho^h y_t, \sigma^2 \left(\frac{1 - \rho^{2h}}{1 - \rho^2}\right)\right), \quad t, h \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

271 If an observation y_t is missing, we let its value be given by the most recently observed realization of $\{y_t\}$.

272 For a thorough forecast evaluation, HMM forecasts are also benchmarked against two regression-based
 273 reference models. The first is a linear regression assuming Gaussian, conditionally independent errors, using the
 274 same covariates as the *ZIB* HMM. The second reference model incorporates the zero-inflated beta distribution
 275 from Eq. (1) with covariate dependence defined in Eq. (6), but without the HMM state dependence. This
 276 corresponds to the *ZIB* regression model proposed by Ospina and Ferrari (2012). Both models are determined
 277 with maximum likelihood estimation. For the *ZIB* regression, this amounts to maximizing the log-likelihood

278 given by

$$\ell_T = \sum_{t=1}^T \ell_t(p_t) + \sum_{\forall t|y_t \in (0,1)} \ell_t(\mu_t, \phi_t), \quad \text{where}$$

$$\ell_t(p_t) = \mathbb{1}_{y_t=0} \log(p_t) + (1 - \mathbb{1}_{y_t=0}) \log(1 - p_t), \quad \text{and}$$

$$\ell_t(\mu_t, \phi_t) = \log(\Gamma(\phi_t)) - \log(\Gamma(\mu_t \phi_t)) - \log(\Gamma((1 - \mu_t) \phi_t)) + (\phi_t - 2) y'_t + (\mu_t \phi_t - 1) y_t^*,$$

279 with $y'_t = \log(1 - y_t)$, $y_t^* = \log(y_t/(1 - y_t))$, $\mathbb{1}_{y_t=0}$ denoting an indicator function, and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ the gamma function.

280 In summary, the AR(1) model represents basic temporal predictability, the \mathcal{ZIB} regression model represents
 281 covariate-based predictability under appropriate distributional assumptions, and the linear regression model
 282 provides a simpler covariate-based reference. Benchmarking the HMM forecasts against these predictors yields
 283 a comprehensive test of the gains from modeling temporal and covariate-dependent dynamics, as well as from
 284 specifying an appropriate distribution.

285 3.2 Metrics

286 When predicting an uncertain future, forecasts should take the form of probability distributions instead of
 287 single-valued quantities (Gneiting and Katzfuss, 2014). Forecasting distributions rather than points quantifies
 288 prediction uncertainty, which is essential to robust decision-making. A well-established metric for evaluation
 289 of predictive distributions is the continuous ranked probability score (CRPS) since it serves to assess both
 290 calibration and sharpness (Gneiting and Katzfuss, 2014). Given a set of predictive distributions f_{Y_t} and a set
 291 of observed values y_t for $t = 1, \dots, T$, we have that

$$\overline{\text{CRPS}} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \int_0^1 [F_{Y_t}(y_t) - H(x - y_t)]^2 dx, \quad (12)$$

292 where F_{Y_t} is the predictive cumulative distribution function, and $H(x - y_t)$ is the Heaviside function which is 0
 293 if $x < y_t$ and 1 otherwise (Gebetsberger et al., 2018). The use of CRPS for evaluation of probabilistic forecasts
 294 of icing-induced power loss on wind turbines is in accordance with Strauss et al. (2022).

295 The average log score is another typical way of evaluating the predictive performance of a probabilistic model,
 296 i.e. $\overline{\log S} = 1/T \sum_{t=1}^T f_{Y_t}(y_t)$ (Gneiting and Katzfuss, 2014). However, for comparing discrete-continuous
 297 distributions with purely continuous ones, this metric is not suitable, since density values cannot be directly
 298 compared to discrete probability masses. One solution to this issue would be to discretize the entire unit domain
 299 into small segments, whereby probability masses are available everywhere. For the purpose of this study, we
 300 rely on the CRPS metric because this score is inherently well-suited for evaluating discrete-continuous forecast
 301 distributions as it is based on the CDF rather than the PDF. Furthermore, it has previously been shown to be
 302 more robust than the log score (Bjerregård et al., 2021).

303 4 Case study: Icing on wind turbine blades

304 Accumulation of ice loads on wind turbines lead to reduced power output (Gao and Hu, 2021). As standard
 305 weather forecasts do not contain ice-growth predictions, power forecasts are subject to large errors during
 306 icing events (Davis, 2014). Given the model proposed in Section 2 with the evaluation setting outlined in
 307 Section 3, we present here our case study in forecasting icing-induced power loss on wind turbines. The case
 308 study is structured as follows: Section 4.1 describes the considered prediction situation, Section 4.2 presents
 309 the empirical foundation, Section 4.3 details model estimation, while Section 4.4 evaluates the results of the
 310 conducted forecast analysis.

311 4.1 Forecast situation

312 Our forecasting approach is chosen such that the conducted experiments mimic a realistic forecasting setting
 313 emphasizing that historical information is used only when it has been revealed by time. Say that the forecasting
 314 task is to produce a 12-hour ahead forecast of icing-induced power loss based on measured observations at the
 315 wind farm and numerical weather predictions covering that time horizon. Naturally, a forecaster prefers to use
 316 the most updated weather information. The measured information at the wind farm is available in real-time
 317 implying that icing-induced power loss can be quickly inferred such that the history up to the current time is
 318 assumed known.

319 An updated numerical weather prediction (NWP) becomes available twice a day, i.e., at 00:00 and 12:00. The
 320 NWP is provided with a time stamp - its “forecast run” expressing the time at which the NWP is created. Due
 321 to the computational load of running a mesoscale weather model such as ECMWF, there is a delay between
 322 the forecast run and when this information is actually available to the company (see ECMWF (2024) for a
 323 dissemination schedule). The forecast situation is sketched in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Mimicked forecast situation. “OBS” refers to available measurements at the wind farm. s denotes the length of the forecast window.

324 In the mimicked daily forecast operation, the delay is 6 hours. Subsequently, new NWPs are available to the
 325 company at 06:00 and 18:00. If we want to use the NWP from forecast run 00:00 for prediction, the forecast
 326 can (at the earliest) be produced at time 06:00. The relevant weather information that can be extracted from
 327 the NWP (covering the “forecast window”) from forecast run 00:00 for a 12-hour ahead forecast and 6 hour
 328 delay subsequently starts at 18:00. As wind farm observations are available in real-time, the latest known

329 measurements in the prescribed situation are time 06:00 for which the forecast has to be produced. Every time
330 a new NWP becomes available (every 12th hour), the forecast window is shifted 12 hours ahead.

331 4.2 Empirical setting

332 We consider three wind power plants in cold climate during the months from October until April over three
333 consecutive seasons. Data has been anonymized as it comes from a commercial setting where it is a critical
334 foundation of daily operation.

335 4.2.1 Icing-induced power loss

336 An icing signal is induced from the production loss of the whole wind power plant given an expected power
337 output. Thus, it is bounded from above and below by 1 and 0, respectively. The icing signal is provided by
338 industrial collaborators as a univariate time series, so it is an input in the present study. Better forecasts of
339 icing-induced power loss can be directly incorporated into wind power forecasts, since the ice signal is essentially
340 a relative forecast error of an operating wind power prediction tool believed to be caused by icing on the turbine
341 blades.

Figure 4: Observed power output as a percentage of time-dependent plant capacity wrt. measured wind speeds with color-indicated icing signal.

342 In Fig. 4, we show the normalized observed power production wrt. the observed wind speed. The icing
343 signal is indicated by color. The observations without related icing follow an S-shaped power curve. When ice
344 is detected, the power output is displaced downwards with respect to the S-curve. The downward displacement
345 increases when the level of icing increases. A time series visualization of the icing signal has already been
346 provided in Fig. 1 on page 2.

347 Across the three wind farms, the icing signals are subject to strong zero-inflation. Between 12–14% of the
348 observations are missing, and among the non-missing values, the share of exact zeros ranges from 69% to 86%.
349 Exact ones occur rarely (about 1–2% of all observations). The descriptive statistics displayed in Table 1 are

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of icing signals across the wind farms.

	Wind Farm A	Wind Farm B	Wind Farm C
Data coverage			
Share of zeros	0.86	0.69	0.78
Share of ones	0.01	0.01	0.02
Share of missing values	0.12	0.14	0.14
Event characteristics			
Number of icing events	185	206	286
Mean event duration (hours)	9.68	18.67	9.63
Median event duration (hours)	7.00	12.00	6.00
Maximum event duration (hours)	81	166	91
Icing intensity (non-zero)			
Mean intensity (non-zero)	0.28	0.35	0.32
Median intensity (non-zero)	0.14	0.27	0.18
25th percentile intensity (non-zero)	0.04	0.14	0.05
75th percentile intensity (non-zero)	0.39	0.54	0.54

350 based on the icing signal with hourly resolution for all three winters, meaning that windfarm has approx. 5100
351 observations for each winter. Table 1 shows that icing typically occurs in distinct events of limited duration,
352 with median lengths of 6–12 hours and maxima ranging from 81 to 166 hours. Note that we define an event as
353 a sequence of time steps where the icing variable is larger than one and not missing, with each such contiguous
354 run counted as one event. When icing is present, the average power loss lies between 0.28 and 0.35, with
355 distributions that are right-skewed: lower quartiles around 0.04–0.14 and upper quartiles around 0.39–0.54.

356 Further, we note that there is no strong empirical correlation between the daily number of missing ob-
357 servations and the average icing level during a day (Pearson $r \approx 0.132$), suggesting that it is reasonable to
358 assume that values in the icing signal are missing by random. This is in accordance with the assumptions of
359 the proposed HMM in Section 2.

360 4.2.2 Numerical weather predictions

361 The NWP data come from the HRES model (ECMWF, 2023b). The NWP data are based on 12-hour ahead
362 predictions taking the 6-hour delay into account from the forecast run. We extracted predicted variables from
363 historical archives with forecast runs 00:00 and 12:00, all of which are believed to impact atmospheric ice
364 accretion (ISO Standard, 2017). In Appendix A, all weather variables retrieved are listed. Height interpolation
365 is given by the closest vertical grid point to the average turbine hub height of the wind farm.

366 Preliminary data analysis reveals that none of the retrieved variables are strongly correlated with the icing
367 signal, also when interactions and lagged effects are taken into account². Two of the best correlated NWPs with
368 the icing signal are temperature and cloud base height, predicting the height above ground in meters from the
369 base of the lowest cloud layer (ECMWF, 2023b). If cloud base height is considerably larger than the turbine
370 heights, it is unlikely that ice accretes on the turbine blades due to in-cloud icing (which is believed to be the
371 most frequent cause of atmospheric ice accretion (Makkonen, 2000)). A logistic transformation is applied such

²We also tested whether orthogonal projections on the eigenvectors of the NWP dispersion matrices (principal component analysis) could increase correlation. However, this approach did not yield substantial improvements in terms of correlation nor predictive power.

372 that we obtain a proxy variable that is large when clouds are likely to surround the turbines and close to zero
 373 when days are sunny (or almost sunny), i.e.,

$$\widetilde{\text{Cbh}} = \frac{1}{1 + a \exp(b \cdot \text{Cbh})} \quad (13)$$

374 where $a = 0.01$ and $b = 0.015$ ensuring that the proxy cloud base height is scaled properly and increases fast
 375 when the cloud base gets close to the turbine hubs. Eq. (13) ensures that $\widetilde{\text{Cbh}} \approx 1$ when $\text{Cbh} \leq \text{hh}$, and
 376 $\widetilde{\text{Cbh}} \approx 0$ when $\text{Cbh} > 3 \cdot \text{hh}$, with “hh” denoting the average hub height of the wind farm.

377 4.3 Remarks on estimation and implementation

378 **Transformation.** The discrete-continuous stochastic process $\{Y_t : t \in \mathbb{N}\}$ from Section 2 is defined on $[0, 1)$.
 379 However, as shown in Fig. 1, the actual measured icing-induced power loss is defined on the entire standard
 380 unit interval. To squeeze the signal from $[0, 1]$ to $[0, 1)$, we apply the transformation

$$\tilde{y} = \frac{y}{1 + ay}.$$

381 The reasoning is that since the empirical distribution of the icing signal is only slightly one-inflated (see Fig. 1),
 382 there is no need to describe the one-inflation explicitly, as opposed to the case of zero-inflation. We hereby
 383 avoid increasing the number of parameters to be estimated. We use $a = 0.01$.

384 **Batch estimation.** Given the data presented in Section 4.2, we seek to determine the parameters of the \mathcal{ZIB}
 385 HMMs with and without covariates from Section 2, and the baseline predictors from Section 3, by maximizing
 386 the log-likelihood of the models using Eq. (9). As data from three winter seasons are available, we perform
 387 batch estimation on the 1st season, while the two remaining are retained for forecast evaluation.

388 **Model implementation.** The models are implemented in C++, interfaced with R via Rcpp (Eddelbuettel and
 389 Balamuta, 2018) and the C++ Template Model Builder (TMB) framework (Kristensen et al., 2016). TMB enables
 390 exact gradient calculation of the HMM forward algorithm in Eq. (8) via automatic differentiation (AD), using
 391 the CppAD package (Bell, 2003). From this scheme, we avoid finite-difference approximations, which are known
 392 to be both slow and potentially inaccurate. The log-likelihood maximization is performed by Newton–Raphson
 393 algorithm with line search via `nlm` from R Core Team (2022).

394 **Model selection.** Model selection for HMMs consists of two components: 1) selecting the number of hidden
 395 states m , and 2) selecting covariates when applicable. We follow a forward selection procedure to determine m ,
 396 using Akaike’s Information Criterion (AIC) on the 1st season data, that is:

- 397 1. Initialize with $m = 2$.
- 398 2. Estimate parameters $\hat{\theta}$ using Eq. (9).

399 3. Compute Akaike’s Information Criterion, that is $AIC = 2k - 2\ell(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}; Y_t)$.

400 4. Set $m \leftarrow m + 1$, re-estimate, and repeat Step 3. Stop when the AIC no longer decreases.

401 This forward selection balances model fit and parsimony, and in practice resulted in models with between 3 and
402 6 states depending on the specific wind farm and regression setting.

403 For the matter of covariates, we use temperature and the logistically transformed cloud base height while
404 all other NWP’s from Table 6 are omitted, thus $\mathbf{V}_t = (\text{Temp}_t, \widetilde{\text{Cbh}}_t)$.³

405 **Reference predictors.** The model parameters of the AR(1) are determined by maximum likelihood esti-
406 mation using the `stats` library (R Core Team, 2022). Missing values are imputed using linear interpolation.
407 We investigated whether extensions to the AR(1) model could improve performance, by estimating ARIMA
408 models with `auto.arima` from the `forecast` library (Hyndman and Khandakar, 2008). The results of these
409 experiments revealed that the `auto.arima` function selected the AR(1) model as the best one, underlining the
410 appropriateness of the selected benchmark.

411 The *ZIB* regression model and the linear regression model described in Section 3.1 are implemented in C++,
412 interfaced with R via `Rcpp` (Eddelbuettel and Balamuta, 2018). Model parameters are determined by maximum
413 likelihood estimation.

414 4.4 Results and Discussion

415 This section assesses the predictive accuracy via error metrics from Section 3.2, comments on the regression
416 settings, investigates typical prediction values and the time-varying predictive distribution.

417 4.4.1 Model fitting and interpretation

418 Following the forward model selection procedure, different numbers of hidden states were selected across the
419 three sites. For Wind Farm A, the best *ZIB* HMM without covariates was a 4-state model, while the covariate-
420 dependent versions selected 6 states for the transition regression and 3 states for the density regression. For
421 Wind Farm B, the plain *ZIB* HMM selected 6 states, compared to 3 states for the transition regression and 4
422 states for the density regression. For Wind Farm C, the selected models were more balanced, with 4 states for
423 the plain *ZIB* HMM as well as for both covariate-dependent variants. Estimation times varied with model size
424 and covariate setting, ranging between 1–10 seconds.

425 The choice of the number of states reflects how the Markov transition matrix partitions the dynamics of
426 the icing process into persistent regimes. For example, some states correspond to near-zero icing with high
427 diagonal values in the transition probability matrix, while others capture moderate or severe icing with different
428 persistence and switching behavior. To exemplify this structure, we provide the state-dependent distribution

³For brevity of notation, we here write $\mathbf{V}_t = (\text{Temp}_t, \widetilde{\text{Cbh}}_t)$. However, for the regression setting in Section 2.2.1, it is in fact $\mathbf{X}_t = \mathbf{Z}_t = \mathbf{W}_t = (\text{Temp}_t, \widetilde{\text{Cbh}}_t)$, implying that all density parameters have been regressed on the same information, as this proved to perform best in terms of AIC. The remaining covariates from Table 6 were omitted because they did not lower AIC.

429 parameters for the 4-state ZIB HMM model at Wind Farm C in Table 2 together with the estimated transition
 430 probability matrix in Table 3.

Table 2: Maximum likelihood estimated state-dependent distribution parameters.

	Mean (μ)	Precision (ϕ)	Zero-inflation (p)
State 1	0.999	20.56	1.00
State 2	0.771	3.06	0.00
State 3	0.023	39.98	0.12
State 4	0.203	10.05	0.00

Table 3: Maximum likelihood estimated transition probability matrix.

	State 1	State 2	State 3	State 4
State 1	0.985	0.000	0.015	0.000
State 2	0.017	0.931	0.002	0.050
State 3	0.013	0.000	0.812	0.175
State 4	0.098	0.042	0.007	0.853

431 The parameter estimates suggest the following interpretation of the latent regimes: State 1) represents dry
 432 conditions with $\mu \approx 1$, strong zero inflation ($p \approx 1$); State 2) represents high icing intensity ($\mu \approx 0.77$) but
 433 low precision; State 3) represents weak but non-negligible icing ($\mu \approx 0.02$) with substantial probability mass at
 434 zero ($p \approx 0.12$), capturing intermittent, low-level icing; State 4) represents moderate icing ($\mu \approx 0.20$), acting
 435 as a bridge between light and more intense regimes. Note that a zero inflation of 100% in state 1 leads to very
 436 high uncertainty in the beta distribution parameters for that state. To illustrate this, Appendix B shows the
 437 corresponding profile log-likelihoods, which are flat for state 1.

438 As visible from the transition probability matrix, the one-step-ahead probability of remaining in the current
 439 state is high (especially for states related to low-icing), indicating persistence within each regime. However,
 440 taking the 12-step power of the matrix reveals that regime switching becomes much more likely: after 12 hours,
 441 the probability of remaining in the same state typically drops to around 50–60% or lower, reflecting the time
 442 scales at which transitions between icing regimes occur.

443 4.4.2 Assessment of predictive performance

444 As HMMs are probabilistic models, we stress the importance of adequate evaluation metrics to assess proba-
 445 bilistic predictions. As argued in Section 3, to assess the predictive performance of mixed discrete-continuous
 446 distributions, CRPS is suitable. For consistency with the broader forecast literature (Hyndman, 2010), we also
 447 include a point-wise evaluation. For single-valued forecast evaluation in terms of mean absolute error (MAE),
 448 point predictions need to be extracted from the forecasted distributions. Thus, we extract the median from
 449 the predictive distributions as it as a rule of thumb is believed to minimize the MAE. In the following, we will
 450 emphasize CRPS in the comparison of predictive accuracy. The results are provided in Table 4.

451 The AR(1) model outperforms the linear regression, underscoring the strong autocorrelation in the icing
 452 signal relative to the weak predictive power of the available covariates. The zero-inflated beta regression improves
 453 upon the linear regression baseline, confirming the importance of specifying an appropriate distribution even
 454 without explicit temporal dynamics.

455 The ZIB HMMs provide consistent gains in predictive accuracy compared to all baselines. For Wind
 456 Farm A, the non-covariate HMM yields substantial improvements, and the best overall performance comes
 457 from the covariate-dependent variants, particularly the density-regression model, which has the lowest CRPS in

Table 4: Average CRPS and MAE for 12-hour ahead forecast on 2nd and 3rd winter data from m -state ZIB HMMs with and without covariates, $\mathbf{V}_t = (\text{Temp}_t, \widetilde{\text{Cbh}}_t)$, in state-dependent densities as well as transition probabilities. Three reference predictors are included, that is an autoregressive model, a linear regression model, and a zero-inflated beta regression model (with intercepts). Model estimations are performed on 1st winter data for all three wind farms.

(a) Wind Farm A

	AR(1)	Lin. Reg.	ZIB Reg.	ZIB HMM	ZIB HMM with $\mathbf{\Pi}_t(\mathbf{V}_t)$	ZIB HMM with $\mathbf{F}_{Y_t \mathbf{V}_t}$
# Hidden States	0	0	0	4	6	3
# Parameters	2	3	9	24	108	33
2 nd wint. CRPS	0.0552	0.1315	0.0459	0.0405	0.0409	0.0360
3 rd wint. CRPS	0.0486	0.1096	0.0315	0.0288	0.0326	0.0278
2 nd wint. MAE	0.0475	0.1128	0.0513	0.0492	0.0485	0.0423
3 rd wint. MAE	0.0366	0.8877	0.0330	0.0315	0.0398	0.0329

(b) Wind Farm B

	AR(1)	Lin. Reg.	ZIB Reg.	ZIB HMM	ZIB HMM with $\mathbf{\Pi}_t(\mathbf{V}_t)$	ZIB HMM with $\mathbf{F}_{Y_t \mathbf{V}_t}$
# Hidden States	0	0	0	6	3	4
# Parameters	2	3	9	48	27	48
2 nd wint. CRPS	0.0772	0.1136	0.0948	0.0612	0.0597	0.0623
3 rd wint. CRPS	0.0745	0.1050	0.0842	0.0574	0.0575	0.0567
2 nd wint. MAE	0.0799	0.1393	0.1172	0.0808	0.0780	0.0829
3 rd wint. MAE	0.0743	0.1386	0.1029	0.0718	0.0738	0.0699

(c) Wind Farm C

	AR(1)	Lin. Reg.	ZIB Reg.	ZIB HMM	ZIB HMM with $\mathbf{\Pi}_t(\mathbf{V}_t)$	ZIB HMM with $\mathbf{F}_{Y_t \mathbf{V}_t}$
# Hidden States	0	0	0	4	4	4
# Parameters	2	3	9	24	48	48
2 nd wint. CRPS	0.1044	0.1067	0.0777	0.0708	0.0717	0.0713
3 rd wint. CRPS	0.0843	0.0871	0.0504	0.0491	0.0518	0.0473
2 nd wint. MAE	0.0935	0.1236	0.0932	0.0896	0.0919	0.0892
3 rd wint. MAE	0.0611	0.1010	0.0551	0.0548	0.0618	0.0547

458 both winters. For Wind Farm B and C, all three HMM formulations perform similarly, with slight differences
459 depending on the metric and season. The gains over the zero-inflated regression are substantial for Wind Farm
460 B, but minor for Wind Farm C. Overall, these results demonstrate that the ZIB HMM framework outperforms
461 the reference predictors, though the relative benefit of covariate inclusion varies by site.

462 4.4.3 Regression setting

463 For Wind Farm A, regressing the density parameters on covariates yields the most accurate forecasts, while for
464 Wind Farm B the transition-regression model performs best. For Wind Farm C, the HMMs with and without
465 covariates perform similarly with only modest differences. These findings are informative because they can
466 guide the choice of which regression setting to select.

467 As noted by Zucchini and MacDonald (2009), regressing on the transition probabilities has a particularly
468 intuitive interpretation: it allows covariates to influence the persistence and switching behavior of the latent

469 states, which is often easier to communicate to practitioners. In contrast, regressing the state-dependent distri-
470 bution parameters affects the conditional response within each state, and is therefore less transparent in terms
471 of latent state dynamics.

472 From a forecasting perspective, our results indicate that neither regression setting is consistently superior
473 across sites. The density-regression can provide more accurate forecasts under lower levels of icing, as for Wind
474 Farm A and C. In contrast, the transition-regression specification appears more accurate under high icing levels
475 (Wind Farm B). The mixed picture for Wind Farm C suggests that in some cases the covariates may not provide
476 sufficient additional information to improve upon the covariate-free HMM. As noted earlier, the icing signal itself
477 exhibits only weak correlations with the available covariates, which may help explain why the improvements
478 from covariate-dependent specifications are modest overall.

479 One implication is that the regression setting should not be chosen a priori but rather guided by data-
480 driven model comparison. More broadly, the results suggest that interpretability and predictive performance do
481 not always align: while transition-regression models are easier to explain in terms of state dynamics, density-
482 regression models may better capture subtle covariate effects on icing intensity. This distinction is practically
483 relevant for forecasting systems, since the choice of regression setting determines not only the forecast accuracy
484 but also the way in which meteorological information is translated into probabilistic predictions.

485 4.4.4 Remarks on metrics

486 CRPS and MAE broadly agree in their ranking of methods, though, as in other studies, CRPS penalizes the
487 Gaussian AR(1) baseline more heavily than MAE due to its distributional mis-specification. Together, the
488 three case studies support the conclusion that *ZIB* HMMs are well suited for probabilistic icing forecasts, while
489 also highlighting that the optimal covariate specification (plain, transition-dependent, or density-dependent) is
490 site-specific.

491 4.4.5 Typical predicted values during icing events

492 To further illustrate the predictive behavior of the models during icing events, Table 5 reports the percentiles
493 of predictive medians, which we refer to as typical single-valued forecasts.

494 The regression-based benchmarks (linear and *ZIB* regression) are limited in their ability to capture the
495 variability of icing intensity, with the *ZIB* regression in particular collapsing to forecasts of exactly zero across
496 all sites and seasons (due to the zero inflation and the weak correlation between icing and the regressors). The
497 AR(1) model provides non-trivial forecasts but with wide predictive intervals, reflecting the inadequacy of the
498 Gaussian assumption for bounded data. By contrast, the *ZIB* HMMs produce distributions with point masses
499 at zero and flexible, asymmetric spreads during events, yielding forecasts that are more consistent with the
500 empirical distribution of icing intensity. While the predictive medians of the HMMs often remain close to zero,
501 their intervals adapt to the site-specific and seasonal severity of icing, as seen most clearly at Wind Farm B
502 with its relatively large icing levels.

Table 5: Median, 10th, and 90th percentiles of predictive medians during icing events, along with corresponding percentiles of observed icing levels.

	Wind Farm A	Wind Farm B	Wind Farm C
Winter 2			
Observed icing	0.23 [0.02; 1.00]	0.33 [0.06; 0.97]	0.32 [0.03; 1.00]
AR(1)	0.00 [0.00; 0.77]	0.24 [0.00; 0.78]	0.08 [0.00; 0.58]
Lin. Reg.	0.03 [0.02; 0.08]	0.13 [0.04; 0.22]	0.05 [0.03; 0.15]
<i>ZIB</i> Reg.	0.00 [0.00; 0.00]	0.00 [0.00; 0.00]	0.00 [0.00; 0.00]
<i>ZIB</i> HMM	0.00 [0.00; 0.13]	0.22 [0.00; 0.65]	0.00 [0.00; 0.13]
<i>ZIB</i> HMM with $\mathbf{\Pi}_t(\mathbf{V}_t)$	0.00 [0.00; 0.58]	0.16 [0.00; 0.68]	0.00 [0.00; 0.26]
<i>ZIB</i> HMM with $\mathbf{F}_{Y_t \mathbf{V}_t}$	0.00 [0.00; 0.95]	0.13 [0.00; 0.60]	0.00 [0.00; 0.15]
Winter 3			
Observed icing	0.12 [0.00; 0.71]	0.24 [0.05; 0.73]	0.19 [0.00; 1.00]
AR(1)	0.00 [0.00; 0.41]	0.16 [0.00; 0.54]	0.00 [0.00; 0.63]
Lin. Reg.	0.04 [0.01; 0.09]	0.13 [0.05; 0.21]	0.05 [0.03; 0.16]
<i>ZIB</i> Reg.	0.00 [0.00; 0.00]	0.00 [0.00; 0.00]	0.00 [0.00; 0.00]
<i>ZIB</i> HMM	0.00 [0.00; 0.04]	0.11 [0.00; 0.54]	0.00 [0.00; 0.07]
<i>ZIB</i> HMM with $\mathbf{\Pi}_t(\mathbf{V}_t)$	0.00 [0.00; 0.35]	0.14 [0.00; 0.67]	0.00 [0.00; 0.13]
<i>ZIB</i> HMM with $\mathbf{F}_{Y_t \mathbf{V}_t}$	0.00 [0.00; 0.01]	0.10 [0.00; 0.59]	0.00 [0.00; 0.08]

503 4.4.6 Time-varying predictive distribution

504 In Fig. 5, we illustrate the nature of the time-varying predictive distributions for multiple instances in time before
505 and during an icing event for different predictors from Table 4, that is, the 5-state HMM (green densities), a
506 3-state HMM with covariates in the transition probabilities (blue densities), incl. time series visualizations of
507 the covariates driving the evolution of the transition probabilities in the HMM with exogenous dependencies.
508 The AR(1) model (red densities) is included as a reference.

509 The *ZIB* HMMs have discrete probability masses in $y_t = 0$ which, as seen from Fig. 5, are large in periods
510 with no icing. During no icing periods, the spread of the predicted distribution on the unit interval is smaller
511 than during the icing event. Here, the predicted HMM distributions have smaller probabilities in $y_t = 0$. The
512 5-state HMM has more modes than the 3-state HMM, however both of them are multimodal. Their differences
513 in distribution shape over time indicate that the HMMs are flexible in how probability mass is distributed
514 across the domain. In comparison, the AR(1) model predicts a normal distribution (see Eq. (11)), which during
515 no-icing periods has approximately zero mean, and half of its probability mass located in negative values. The
516 illustration of the differences between the HMMs and AR(1) reflects the differences in their forecast accuracy
517 in Table 4, which motivates the importance of specifying a suitable distribution.

518 Although the Markov property assumes that the future depends only on the current state, this does not
519 exclude modeling persistence or gradual development, which are naturally captured through the transition
520 probabilities. The strong autocorrelation observed in the icing signal is well represented in the fitted HMMs, as
521 seen from their ability to adapt the probability mass during icing and non-icing periods. Nevertheless, richer
522 dependence structures (such as higher-order or hidden semi-Markov formulations) could explicitly incorporate
523 longer-term memory, which goes beyond the scope of this study.

Figure 5: Top: Observed icing-induced power loss (black dotted line) visualized with the predictive distributions of an AR(1) model (red densities), 5-state ZIB HMM (green densities), and a 3-state ZIB HMM with transition rates regressed on covariates (blue densities). Bottom: Weather forecasts of temperature (red line), and predicted cloud base height (Cbh) logistically transformed via Eq. (13) (green line).

524 4.5 Future work

525 There are several extensions relevant for further improving the proposed model setting. In the present study, we
 526 perform batch estimation on the 1st winter, while retaining the 2nd and 3rd winter solely for forecast evaluation.
 527 A possible extension would be to introduce adaptive or recursive methods, either by performing the entire
 528 batch estimation iteratively, introducing forgetting factors, or by rolling estimation windows. Optimum score
 529 estimation could also be considered so parameters are determined using an objective function that is consistent
 530 with the forecast scoring rule used for evaluation (Gneiting and Raftery, 2007).

531 The role of covariates is likely site-specific. In this study, the available covariates correlated only weakly with
 532 the icing signal, which explains the modest gains observed from covariate-dependent specifications. However,
 533 forecasts of accreted ice levels from first-principle models, or improved weather variables, could serve as stronger
 534 predictors. In such cases, the ZIB HMM framework remains directly applicable and can adapt predictions of
 535 icing-related power loss to more informative inputs.

536 Other natural extensions include ensemble forecasts, which are known to improve predictive accuracy (Gneit-
 537 ing and Raftery, 2005), and continuous-time formulations, which would enable a physical interpretation of the
 538 latent states while also facilitating censoring, see for instance Bisgaard et al. (2025). Future work could also
 539 explore alternatives to the beta distribution, such as the Kumaraswamy distribution, which is computationally
 540 simpler and has a closed-form cumulative distribution function, though it is less commonly applied in
 541 probabilistic time-series settings.

542 **5 Conclusion**

543 We propose *ZIB* HMM models to forecast bounded and inflated time series with missing observations, incorpo-
544 rating covariates via the state-dependent density parameters and the transition probabilities. The models are
545 tested in a forecast case study, producing 12-hour ahead predictions for icing-induced power loss on wind tur-
546 bines with weather forecasts constituting exogenous information. The probabilistic forecasts are evaluated with
547 the continuous ranked probability score, and extracted medians from the predictive distributions are evaluated
548 by the mean absolute error. We benchmark against an AR(1) model, a zero-inflated beta regression model, and
549 a linear regression model. We conclude that the *ZIB* HMM performs with highest predictive accuracy. Density
550 regression improved accuracy at sites with lower icing levels, while transition regression performed better under
551 more severe icing conditions. In line with earlier findings, the explanatory power of the available covariates was
552 limited, which explains why the performance gains from covariate inclusion were modest overall. The results
553 of the present study indicate that the robustness of traditionally used power forecasts can be increased during
554 icing events.

555 **Data statement**

556 Due to sensitivity of data, raw data is confidential and cannot be shared. The wind power plant is anonymized
557 incl. any temporal or geographical specificities. Further information is available from the authors.

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A Retrieved weather variables from ECMWF

Table 6: Numerical weather predictions retrieved from ECMWF. See ECMWF (2023b) for further specification.

Variable name	Abbreviation	Unit
Standard variables		
Temperature	t	°C
Wind speed	ws	m s ⁻¹
Specific humidity	q	kg kg ⁻¹
Wind direction	wdir	Angular °
Logarithm of surface pressure	lnsp	–
Specific water content		
Specific rain water content	crwc	kg kg ⁻¹
Specific snow water content	cswc	kg kg ⁻¹
Specific cloud liquid water content	clwc	kg kg ⁻¹
Specific cloud ice water content	ciwc	kg kg ⁻¹
Cloud variables		
Cloud base height	cbh	m
Cloud low cover	lcc	–
Cloud medium cover	mcc	–
Cloud high cover	hcc	–
Total column content		
Total column cloud liquid water	tclw	kg m ⁻²
Total column cloud ice water	tciw	kg m ⁻²
Total column liquid water anomaly	tclwa	kg m ⁻²
Total column water	tcw	kg m ⁻²

674 **B Profile log-likelihood**

Figure 6 shows the profile log-likelihoods of the parameters related to the beta distribution in Table 2.

Figure 6: Profile log-likelihood of state-dependent distribution parameters related to the beta distributions in the 4-state *ZIB* HMM estimated on 1st winter data for Wind Farm C.